

Next FOOD

EDUCATING THE NEXT GENERATION
OF PROFESSIONALS IN THE AGRIFOOD SYSTEM

D6.7: Practice abstracts part 1 – before the first review meeting

WP6– Working Package Title Here

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Executive summary

Deliverable 6.7 contains the first set of Practice Abstracts to feed into to the website of the European Innovation Partnership Agricultural Productivity and Sustainability (EIP-AGRI) for broad dissemination to practitioners - farmers, farmers' groups, advisors, researchers and all other stakeholders of the agrifood and forestry systems in a concise and easily understandable way.

Practice Abstracts (PAs) follow a common dissemination format containing a short summary which describes the main information/recommendations/practice that can serve the end-users in their daily practice.

In total 100 Practice Abstracts will be collected and submitted during the duration of NextFood and they will all feed into the EIP-AGRI website and as here be part of deliverables D6.7, D6.8 and D6.9.

All Practice Abstracts have been numbered and will hereinafter be referred to as "PA".

1 PA#1: A kick-of workshop for learning and engagement

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 1	Partner	SLU, Sweden
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Short title in English	A kick-of workshop for learning and engagement
Short title in native language	En Upp-Start Workshop för lärande och engagemang
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The Nextfood consortium consists of 19 organisations in the education sector and a number of stakeholder organisations representing different parts of the agrifood system. In order to achieve an institutional change within higher education, the Nextfood consortium must learn how to learn together, and become what is usually referred to as a learning community. The kick-off meeting was planned to communicate purpose, aims and roles of partners, as well as to start up the learning process of the consortium. The premises of such a workshop is to be democratic and inclusive. In this practice abstract we present the overall planning of the kick-off workshop:</p> <p>Workshop sequence:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Welcome session. Introduction to the project, presentation of goals and objectives. 2) Presentation of consortium members. Plenary start-up exercise. Small group discussion. 3) The project excellence (Nextfood model) is presented. Reflection and discussion. 4) Identification of challenges when it comes to project design, organization and economy. 5) How to plan for case-based research. One example is presented. 6) A shift in mindset. Re-visit the Nextfood model and introduction to dialogue. 7) Planning session for the different work packages. 8) Wrap-up session. Discussion, what we have achieved? What is still unclear? Making an action plan and evaluation of the workshop.
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Konsortiet inom Nextfood består av 19 organisationer inom utbildningssektorn samt ett antal intressenter som representerar olika delar av livsmedelssystemet. För att åstadkomma en förändring på institutionell nivå inom högre utbildning, måste Nextfoods konsortium lära sig att lära tillsammans, och bli ett så kallat lärande community. Uppstartsmötet var planerat till att kommunicera syfte, mål och deltagarnas roller, samt att påbörja lärandeprocessen för konsortiet. Kraven på en sådan workshop är att den ska vara demokratisk och bygga på delaktighet. I detta practice abstract presenterar vi den övergripande planeringen av denna uppstarts workshop.</p> <p>Programmets delar:</p>

	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Välkomstsession. Introduktion till projektet, presentation av mål och syften. 2) Presentation av konsortiets deltagare. Introduktionsövning i helklass. Diskussion i smågrupper. 3) Projektets excellence (Nextfood modellen) presenteras. Reflektion och diskussion. 4) Identifiering av utmaningar när det gäller projektets design, organisering och ekonomi. 5) Hur kan man planera för aktionsbaserad forskning i fallstudier? Ett exempel presenteras. 6) Ett skifte i synsätt. Rekapitulation av Nextfoods modell och en introduktion till dialog. 7) Planering av arbetet i de olika arbetspaketen. 8) Avslutningssession. Diskussion, vad har vi uppnått? Vad är fortfarande oklart? Gör en handlingsplan och en utvärdering av programmet.
Link	

2 PA#2: Dissemination, exploitation and outreach plan

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 2	Partner	AFS, Greece
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Short title in English	Max 150 characters
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Link	[...]

3 PA#3: Action Research Protocol

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 3	Partner NMBU, Norway
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Short title in English	Action research protocol
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Action research is essentially learning by doing, and reflecting upon the experiences. An intuitive approach recommended for anyone who is trying to improve a situation they are in. A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In order to ensure a synchronised data collection, this research protocol provides instructions on how to gather and analyse data from the activities performed during the case work. This involves recording workshops, gathering the responses from students and teachers and synthesising these in a streamlined fashion. The protocol ensures that all cases have a shared research strategy, but also allows each case to fit the data collection to their specific context.</p> <p>By doing research this way we will get an improved understanding of what it takes to implement alternative education models that are better fit to deal with present and future challenges. Simultaneously we will improve the education for the learners who are involved in the cases so that they are already better equipped to deal with the complex challenges.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	Not relevant
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LfPTVtX6SoWONC1INo1

4 PA#4: Review of existing standards and criteria for evaluation of action learning education and applied research

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 4	Partner	USB, Czech Republic
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Short title in English	Review of existing standards and criteria for evaluation of action learning education and applied research
Short title in native language	Přehled existujících standardů a kritérií pro hodnocení aktivního vzdělávání a aplikovaného výzkumu
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>This research is aimed to information on evaluation and evaluation tools in terms of agricultural and food processing applied research and education. The education and namely the applied research are often evaluated through standard methods aimed to scientometric criteria, which is not always the best solution. These ways of assessment enable to express only in a limited extent detailed full range of applied research/education effects. Therefore, it is necessary to look for alternatives. The main part of the research is divided into chapters evaluating applied research and others evaluating the education. Present evaluation methods are included and there are assessing standards specified in more details for each of the fields. Further, there are addressed the main indicators for education/ applied research, whereas especially stressed there are social indicators. This field is omitted in many of present standard evaluation systems, or addressed only superficially. The research serves namely as a source for the subsequent creation of the frame of innovated evaluating tools for education and applied research in terms of food processing and agricultural sphere. Based on this research, there are prepared publications that set themselves a goal to point out the main problems and imperfections of present evaluation models and to propose options of their improvements.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Rešerše je zaměřena na informace o hodnocení a hodnotících nástrojích v rámci zemědělského a potravinářského aplikovaného výzkumu a vzdělávání. Jak vzdělávání, tak zejména aplikovaný výzkum je často hodnocen standardními metodami zaměřenými na scientometrická kritéria, což však není vždy optimální řešení. Tyto formy posuzování umožňují jen v limitované míře postihnout do hloubky plnou škálu dopadů aplikovaného výzkumu/vzdělávání a je proto potřeba k nim hledat alternativy. Hlavní část rešerše je rozdělena na kapitoly věnující se hodnocení aplikovaného výzkumu a kapitoly věnující se vzdělávání. Zahrnutý jsou současné metody hodnocení a pro obě oblasti zvláště jsou detailněji popsány hodnotící standardy. Pro vzdělávání i aplikovaný výzkum jsou dále řešeny hlavní indikátory, přičemž zvláštní důraz je věnován indikátorům sociálním. Tato oblast je v řadě současných standardních hodnotících systémů opomíjena, nebo řešena pouze</p>

	<p>povrchně. Rešerše slouží zejména jako podkladový materiál pro navazující tvorbu rámce inovovaných hodnotících nástrojů pro vzdělávání a aplikovaný výzkum v rámci potravinářského a zemědělského sektoru. Na jejím základě jsou připravovány publikace, které si kladou za cíl zdůraznit hlavní problémy a nedostatky v současných modelech hodnocení a navrhnout možnosti jejich zdokonalení.</p>
Link	<p>https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-Lq2P2ZzwGK2REPWF5XD</p>

5 PA#5: NextFood Website

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 5	Partner	AFS, Greece
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Short title in English	Max 150 characters
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Link	[...]

6 PA#6: Master Manual for Case Development, first draft

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 6	Partner	NMBU, Norway
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Short title in English	Master manual for case development, first draft
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, the case leaders will find specific instructions on how to develop their case towards the transformational goals of the project. Primarily, this document describes the iterative process of planning, implementing and reflecting, which is to be followed by each case. Specific instructions are given to each of the three phases and appendices contain templates in relation to those specific instructions as well as examples from the past cycle of project activities. We recommend anyone interested in trying out these action learning elements to have a look at these instructions and appendices.</p> <p>We believe that a successful transition to a situation where action learning is the norm for educating the future generation of professionals, we need to concretise and make guidelines as to how such an approach is done. This document constitutes one of the pillars of the foundation upon which the next generation of education system is built. This manual is written in such a way that it should be easily accessible for practitioners who would like to adapt to the Nextfood approach.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LfPUonWVI5baDp3Jqds

7 PA#7: Case Development Report, year 1

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 7	Partner	NMBU, Norway
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Short title in English	Case development report, year 1
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, we report the activities and outcomes in each Nextfood case throughout the first year of the project. Each case has reported on the process and outcomes of following the instructions for how to run their case and research the process.</p> <p>The first year of the case work was heavily focused on initiating the case work. For many cases, this meant transforming an already existing course from their standard way of operating to something closer to the action learning-based Nextfood approach. Kick-off workshops were conducted in most cases where students, teachers, administration and other key stakeholders co-developed the strategy for kicking off the transformation process. Common for many cases was the fact that this change was very much welcomed by both students and teachers. A key challenge that was identified was how to find resources and time to enable the necessary change to happen. The local institutions might play a key role in enabling an improved focus on action learning.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LfPZ27Zd_GjTADikZqy

8 PA#8: MSc. Agroecology Course: Action learning in Farming and Food Systems

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 8	Partner	NMBU, Norway
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Short title in English	MSc. Agroecology course: Action learning in Farming and Food Systems
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Main results: During the introductory course of the Agroecology master program, the students dive into farming and food systems and try to facilitate change. Through the interactions with the real-life cases, the students develop not only knowledge about the systems, but more importantly they also develop the competences needed to engage with them. In addition to the case work, through various sessions and workshops, the students practice five core competences: observation, reflection, dialogue, visioning and participation. The goal is that by focusing on developing these competences, the students will become life-long learners who can contribute to facilitating improvements of farming and food systems in their future careers.</p> <p>Main practical recommendations: We believe that by focusing on developing competences rather than only knowledge, we can better equip the next generation of professionals for dealing with the complex issues of today's agrifood and forestry systems. There is little point in educating knowledgeable people if they are not able to use their knowledge for any good. And who doesn't want a competent and knowledgeable colleague? We therefore encourage stakeholders to appreciate and foster the focus on forming a competent generation of professionals.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	N/A
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRYVo6SddSw5eedZxD

9 PA#9: Main practical recommendations of the University of Oradea Course

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 9	Partner	University of Oradea, Romania
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Short title in English	Main practical recommendations of the University of Oradea course
Short title in native language	Recomandări practice pentru cursul organizat de Universitatea din Oradea
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The main key actions before the course starts will be the preparation of training materials (list of topics, theoretical aspects, references, etc) the organisation of a field trip to a partner company relevant for the project that the students are going to work on, meeting the facilitators to discuss the materials that are going to be used during the courses (including the Student learning document, facilitator's documents, assessing methods, quizzes on soft skills/competences, interviews to be taken, feedback from the stakeholders, etc.). The main outcome of this course is that it provides the best and safest environment for high-school students and students to form mixed teams in which they can learn together or one from each other, experience new action-based learning methods and develop new skills (soft skills and technical skills) required on the labour market. Asking the right questions and the reflection are central processes within the group.</p> <p>The whole learning process without guidance of facilitators and specialists from the field will be useless, and in this way the involving of the facilitators and specialists will increase the efficiency of learning.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Principalele acțiuni cheie înainte de începerea cursului vor fi pregătirea materialelor de instruire (listă de subiecte, aspecte teoretice, referințe bibliografice, etc.) organizarea unei excursii pe teren la o companie parteneră relevantă pentru proiectul pe care studenții urmează să-l dezvolte, întâlnirea cu facilitatorii pentru a discuta despre materialele care vor fi utilizate în timpul cursurilor (inclusiv documentul de învățare a studentului, documentele facilitatorului, metode de evaluare, chestionare despre competențe tehnice/ competențe soft, interviurile care trebuie efectuate, feedback din partea părților interesate etc.)</p> <p>Rezultatul principal al acestui curs este faptul că oferă cel mai bun și cel mai sigur mediu pentru elevii de liceu și studenții să formeze echipe mixte în care pot învăța împreună sau unul de la celălalt, să experimenteze noi metode de învățare bazate pe acțiuni și să dezvolte noi abilități (abilități soft și abilități tehnice) necesare pe piața muncii. Deasemenea se va urmări ca, cursanții să învețe să pună întrebările corecte, iar reflecția va fi unul din procesele centrale în cadrul grupului. Întregul proces de învățare, fără a dispune de facilitatori și specialiști din domeniu, ar fi inutil și, în acest fel, implicarea facilitatorilor și specialiștilor va crește eficiența învățării.</p>

Link

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYR_25O3pNtG9S9IkT3

10 PA#10: Small scale farmers contributing to Agroecology education at Farmers' Training Centre in Ethiopia

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 10	Partner	College of Dryland Agriculture and Natural Resources, Mekelle University, Ethiopia
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Short title in English	Small scale farmers contributing to Agroecology education at Farmers' Training Centre in Ethiopia
Short title in native language	NA
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p><u>Main results</u> Farmers' Training Centres (FTC) were established to serve as colleges for the small scale farming community in rural Ethiopia. The Master program in Agroecology and Sustainable Development at Mekelle University used this opportunity to co-create knowledge between the FTC stakeholders, instructors and students through experiential learning based action research program. The courses designed to create this linkage were Agroecological Innovations I and II. The Master program students spent half day orientation with course instructors at the FTC and spent about two hours of time with FTC stakeholders trying to understand the present situation of the farming and food systems. The FTC stakeholders selected representative case sites and client farmers for each student. Students completed the data collection through participatory approaches and generated report for the course evaluation at the University. The students presented their report in front of their client farmers and FTC stakeholders to see how they understood the present situation, envision and recommend in the future situation. This created opportunity for the individual farmers to learn from their peer experience and students opinions. Valuable comments were forwarded to the students from the farming community that contributed in their learning.</p> <p><u>Main recommendation</u> In the process of generating future agricultural professionals it is necessary to link real life problems with the education system. Higher education institutions in agriculture should use this opportunity to co-learn from the existing and new practices among stakeholders. Education programs designed in this way can provide insight for the academic institutions to revise and develop new curriculums that can address local needs on a sustainable basis.</p>

Short summary for practitioners in native language	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYR_RXD9lQxQtK32KoI

11 PA#11: Aquaponics Project Wins Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition

Nextfood Practice Abstract #11	Partner	ISEKI Food-Association, Austria
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Short title in English	Aquaponics Project Wins Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition
Short title in native language	Not applicable
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Main Results: The Sustainable Supply Chain International Student Competition Games are an opportunity for Master students from any food-related study programme to participate in an online competition to develop and design their unique solution to an actual challenge in the food industry. Students voluntarily join this competition which requires i) identifying and solving real problems ii) action-oriented learning to train job-related skills and iii) a speaking opportunity at a professional conference for the winner. The winning project from the 2019 competition in Sustainable Aquaculture was “Towards sustainable awareness: Implementation of an aquaponic code of practice” and will be presented at Aquaculture Europe 2019.</p> <p>Main Practical Recommendations: The value of this real-world participatory student activity, with opportunities for student exploitation in a professional arena, is both to improve student skills and to generate novel ideas to improve food sustainability. Educators can use similar activities in other fields, engaging students and training them in soft and technical skills for the job market. Students take an active part in a series of webinars, engage and exchange ideas with external experts and with the other student teams. Students present their solutions in a written report and at a final virtual conference and a team of experts from academia and business evaluate the solutions on the grounds of originality, innovativeness and potential exploitability (application to industry and social, economic and environmental impact). Since food producers and processors partner with educators or professional associations all can benefit from entrepreneurial student ideas, putting winning projects into practice.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language	Not applicable
Link	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-4-supply-chain-innovation-competition/

12 PA#12: Action learning Agriscapes: Enhanced extension service to young farmers based on principles and practices of the Action Learning method

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 12	Partner	American Farm School of Thessaloniki, Greece
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Short title in English	Action learning Agriscapes: Enhanced extension service to young farmers based on principles and practices of the Action Learning method
Short title in native language	Not applicable
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Methodology-expected outcomes</p> <p>In the Greek case study, the methodology of action learning is employed to create groups of heterogeneous actors (learning sets) who engage in collective, discovery-based learning activities, to collaboratively construct new knowledge. In total, three different learning sets have been formed: one focused on livestock farming, one centred on viticulture, and one focused on food processing companies. Each one of the first two groups consists of a farmer, a student of agronomy, an academic, a professional with work experience in the field, and an observer with expertise in knowledge co-production processes. Through a process of discovering problems, proposing and implementing solutions, and reflecting on the procedure of identifying-solving problems, each learning set intends to develop a common understanding of the ways farming is practiced as well as to discover different meanings of farming and agricultural sustainability. This way, each participant helps others to make sense of their experience, while the dialogue and the reflection process leads to a redefinition of the concept of farming. Within this context, students are trying to develop their communication skills, their reflection competencies and their problem-solving skills.</p> <p>Practical implementation</p> <p>Based on the above-mentioned findings and the principles of action learning, a course has been designed and organized and will be held at International Hellenic University during the current semester. The course's curriculum is action-based oriented and after its first implementation and after an assessment process some changes and/or improvements will be carried out in order the students to be more actively engaged in the learning process and to be more competent in terms of communication and problem-solving skills.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language	Not applicable

Link

https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRbPvUR1C98ei47xpH

13 PA#13: Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain - Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 13	Partner	Skogforsk, Sweden
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Short title in English	Towards a profitable and sustainable forestry chain - Increased quality and number of micro-habitats for enhanced biodiversity
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Short title in native language	
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Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>There is an increasing interest in balancing economic and environmental aspects during roundwood harvesting from areas with high natural values. There is also an unproven agreement among researchers, forestry personnel and machine operators that a skilled operator often can improve or even create habitats for flora and fauna during certain conditions in an efficient way to a modest extra cost.</p> <p>Skogforsk is running a case aiming at a higher understanding about logging techniques, strategies and methods to increase quality and number of micro-habitats in production forests. Our case is conducted as a vocational course for forestry professionals. We will use the Nextfood model (Figure 1) to develop and implement the course.</p> <p>Figure 1. The Nextfood model for teaching and learning in agrifood and forestry education. The iterative process of planning, implementing and reflecting.</p> <p>After the first meeting conducted at an ongoing logging operation, all participants agreed that the model could be very fruitful to allow researchers, management and operators to learn from each other. As a first step each participant, forestry professionals as well as researchers were asked to write down what they most of all would like to teach the other participants and what they most of all would like to learn. Their answers create a platform for the upcoming case. A planning workshop with the team of researchers was held at Skogforsk in Uppsala in September 2019. During the workshop an activity plan for the first cycle of the Nextfood model was created.</p>
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Short summary for practitioners in native language	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRbc70DWvqfxH1Xe2R https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-6-towards-a-profitable-and-sustainable-forestry-chain/

14 PA#14: Development of sustainable farming systems I+II

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 14	Partner UBS, Czech Republic
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Short title in English	Development of sustainable farming systems I+II
Short title in native language	Projektování udržitelných systémů hospodaření I+II
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The case study focused on the concept of active education is carried out at the Faculty of Agriculture of the University of South Bohemia in České Budějovice as a part of the courses Designing of Ecological Management Systems I and II. The course is realized over a period of two semesters (each semester has twelve weeks, there is a four-hour block reserved for the course every week), and is thematically focused on the application of agroecological practices in designing of agricultural farm and its activities. All three main pillars of agroecology are included - sustainable agricultural activities, the environment and the social sphere. During the course, students in pairs elaborate three projects related to each of the main pillars. That is done in collaboration with external experts who are directly involved in teaching. A significant part of the course takes place directly in an environment related to individual projects (organic farm, protected landscape area, a farm focused on social agriculture and organizations implementing into therapy the green care concept and elements of social farming). A substantial innovation is a change in the approach to education, where teachers transform into the role of discussion moderators between students and representatives of external experts and practice. In addition to providing feedback during the elaboration, the external experts also participate in the final evaluation of student projects.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language	<p>Případová studie zaměřená na koncept aktivního vzdělávání je na Zemědělské fakultě Jihočeské univerzity v Českých Budějovicích realizována v rámci kurzů Projektování udržitelných systémů hospodaření I a II. Kurz je realizován v průběhu dvou semestrů (každý semestr má dvanáct týdnů, v každém týdnu je pro kurz vyhrazen čtyřhodinový blok), tematicky je zaměřen na uplatňování agroekologických postupů v rámci projektování zemědělské farmy a jejích aktivit. Zahrnuty jsou všechny tři hlavní pilíře agroekologie – udržitelná zemědělská činnost, životní prostředí a sociální sféra. V průběhu kurzu studenti řeší ve dvojicích tři projekty směřované ke každému z hlavních pilířů. To se děje ve spolupráci s externími odborníky z praxe, kteří se do výuky přímo zapojují. Podstatná část kurzu probíhá přímo v prostředí vázanému k jednotlivým projektům (ekologická farma, chráněná krajinná oblast, farma zaměřená na sociální zemědělství a organizace realizující v rámci terapií koncept green care a prvky sociálního zemědělství. Podstatnou inovací je změna přístupu ke vzdělávání, kdy se pedagogové posouvají do role moderátorů diskuse mezi studenty a zástupci externích expertů a praxe. Externí odborníci se pak vedle poskytování zpětné</p>

	vazby v průběhu řešení podílejí i na finálním hodnocení studentských projektů.
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LYRbpkNdz6BThyLjATn

15 PA#15: Action learning to become a gastronome: experiential learning links theory and practice and develop students' competencies

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 15	Partner	University of Gastronomic Sciences, Italy
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Short title in English	Action learning to become a gastronome: experiential learning links theory and practice and develop students' competencies
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Main results:</p> <p>Experiential approach is implemented at UNISG since its foundation with study trips. However, Action-learning is developed in a structured way since NEXTFOOD with thematic study trip at Bachelor level and a case base course in agroecology at Master level. The study trip structure includes since last year 3 phases: introduction, thematic cases visits and reflection and restitution using Plenary, Group and Individual (PGI) sessions. This structure is used both for Bachelor and for Master students and the goal is competence development in both knowledge and skills. The Introduction and Reflection sessions stimulate active participation of students both through interpersonal interaction (dialogue) and use of electronic resources (online sources, electronic platform, tools of Google).</p> <p>In addition, this structure stimulate participation and direct dialogue between students and agricultural stakeholders. The students had opportunities to see food production and food processing, and to talk directly to food producers and to players of food supply chain. In turn, the producers could contact to the future professionals and to have their feedback and new ideas.</p> <p>Main practical recommendations:</p> <p>Educators can use this structure in order to provide various learning outcomes such as knowledge acquisition, competence development, practical experience, understanding of existing realities of the agro-food system in a country.</p> <p>The value of this three-phase structure is fostering action learning practices, engagement students in the the learning process, development of specific knowledge and enabling student-stakeholder dialogue.</p>

Short summary for practitioners in native language

Link

<https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-8-experiential-and-action-learning-in-sustainable-gastronomy-it/>

16 PA#16: Three months certificate course in Agroecology at University of Calcutta

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 16	Partner	University of Calcutta and Welthungerhilfe, India
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Short title in English	Three months certificate course in Agroecology at University of Calcutta
Short title in native language	Not applicable
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>Main Results: The 3 months certificate course in agroecology is an opportunity for the farmer trainers, agri-business entrepreneurs, development workers from any agri/food related background to develop and design solutions to an actual challenge in the agri-food system. The pedagogical approach of the course focused to bring a shift in paradigm from a linear to a cyclical approach to learning based on an active action reflection. The main task, was to engage with farms to find out challenges and offer solution. The learning started in an ideal farm and ends with sharing the experience with larger audience through exhibition.</p> <p>Students who joined this course learned</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> i) system dynamics ii) action-oriented learning to train stakeholder iii) solving real life problems in agri-food sectors. <p>The major skills achieved were Observation, Reflection, Visioning, Dialogue, Participation, Communication.</p> <p>The main practical recommendations: Short term impacts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Improved understanding of pedagogical requirements in Agroecological teaching and learning • Students qualified through the course enthusiastic about initiating agro-ecological actions and some are already pursuing the same. <p>Long term impacts:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation of developed and adapted pedagogical methods in other university curricula where possible. • Improved human resource with Agroecological system skills and orientation to initiate restorative actions in agriculture and food system.
Short summary for practitioners in native language	NA
Link	https://www.nextfood-project.eu/case-9-improving-sustainability-in-farming-and-food-systems-by-bringing-in-agroecological-approach-through-action-learning/

17 PA#17:

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 17	Partner	[...]
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Short title in English	Max 150 characters
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Short summary for practitioners in native language	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Link	[...]

18 PA#18

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 18	Partner	[...]
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Short title in English	Max 150 characters
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Short summary for practitioners in native language	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Link	[...]

19 PA#19: Report on the educational strategy, year 1

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 19	Partner	NMBU, Norway
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Short title in English	Report on the educational strategy, year 1
Short title in native language	
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>A central part of the Nextfood project is the 12 case studies conducted in 10 countries on 3 continents. All these cases are attempting to transform their education models to align with the Nextfood approach. Not only are we trying to make the change, but we are also researching the process and the outcomes. In this document, we report on the outcomes of implementing the Nextfood educational strategy during the first year of the project. Throughout the first year, the selected cases have been engaged with initiating their case work, primarily through planning the initial steps of employing the Nextfood approach. The initial reports from carrying out the educational activities suggest that the Nextfood approach is well suited for developing students' required competences in dealing with a complex reality. However, we also observe signs that the approach may be less successful if the implementation is not performed in a comprehensive way. For the coming cycles, we expect to gain a better understanding of the necessary steps needed to successfully implement the Nextfood approach in the selected cases.</p> <p>For practitioners looking to implement elements of action learning related to the Nextfood approach, we recommend to thoroughly plan the activities and to set up a system to gather reflections on the process. We have found that it is necessary to not only learn by doing, but also to reflect upon the experiences. Reflections upon how the first year of implementing the Nextfood approach has gone can be read about in this document.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-LjQ7G7Yrp9yBfjx7Mrr

20 PA#20: How to plan and perform a successful experiential learning workshop

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 20	Partner	SLU, Sweden
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Short title in English	How to plan and perform a successful experiential learning workshop
Short title in native language	Att planera och genomföra en lyckad aktionsbaserad workshop
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>A well planned workshop increases the chances to achieve the goals of the meeting or the conference. First of all, the purpose and the expected learning outcomes of the meeting should be clearly communicated to all participants. In Nextfood the workshops have three distinct phases:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) In the catching-up phase, participants think back of the period of time since the last meeting and all that that has been accomplished. Members are asked to share achievements and challenges (more cognitive) or one thing they are proud of and one thing that they are disappointed with (more emotional). It can be large and small things. 2) To start exploring the topic of the meeting, the participants are invited to respond to one or two open questions. Questions should be phrased in a way that help participants to put words on their experiences and construct new knowledge together with peers. A few minutes of individual reflection, followed by a discussion in small groups (4-5 people) for 10-15 minutes and a short plenary session, helps the group to share and learn. When opening up a new topic area a short introduction helps participants to grasp the context. 3) The final phase is the wrapping-up where participants look at what has been achieved and not achieved (in relation to the expected learning outcomes of the meeting), and what the implications are for the future. <p>It's important to create a group climate that is based on trust and safety so that participants don't feel unease when being confronted in the discussions by their peers. Depending on the background and previous experience, participants might benefit from</p>

	training in dialogue and active listening skills before or as a part of the workshop.
<p>Short summary for practitioners in native language</p>	<p>En välplanerad workshop ökar chanserna till att uppnå målen med mötet eller konferensen. Först av allt, syfte och vilket lärmål som förväntas att uppnås på mötet ska klart och tydligt kommuniceras till alla deltagarna. I Nextfood har dessa workshops tre distinkta faser:</p> <p>1) I återkopplingsfasen tänker deltagarna tillbaka på tidsperioden från föregående möte tills nu och allt som har blivit genomfört. Deltagarna ombeds att dela med sig framgångar och utmaningar (kognitivt innehåll) eller en sak som de är särskilt stolta eller särskilt besvikna över (emotionellt innehåll). Det kan vara små och stora saker.</p> <p>2) För att börja utforska mötets aktuella ämne, ombeds deltagarna att svara på en eller två öppna frågor. Frågorna ska vara formulerade på ett sätt som hjälper deltagarna att sätta ord på deras erfarenheter och att konstruera ny kunskap tillsammans med de andra deltagarna på mötet. Några minuters individuell reflektion, följt av en diskussion i smågrupper (4-5 deltagare) i 10-15 minuter och en kortare diskussion i helklass, stödjer deltagarna att dela med sig och att lära. När man öppnar ett helt nytt ämne kan en kort introduktion hjälpa deltagarna att förstå helheten.</p> <p>3) Det sista steget handlar om att knyta ihop säcken där deltagarna tittar på vad som har uppnåtts och vad som inte har uppnåtts (i relation tillförväntade lärmål), och vad det innebär för framtiden.</p> <p>Det är viktigt att skapa ett gruppklimat som baseras på tillit och trygghet så att deltagarna inte känner sig obekväma när de konfronteras i diskussionen med sina kamrater. Beroende på bakgrund och tidigare erfarenhet, kan deltagarna få en hjälp av träning i dialog och aktivt lyssnande innan de deltar i workshopen.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>[...]</p>

21 PA#21:

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 21	Partner	[...]
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Short title in English	
Short title in native language	Max 150 characters
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Short summary for practitioners in native language	1000-1500 characters, word count, no spaces
Link	[...]

22 PA#22: Analysis of existing policies and programmes regarding education and training in the agrifood and forestry sectors

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 22	Partner	UNIBO
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Short title in English	Analysis of existing policies and programmes regarding education and training in the agrifood and forestry sectors
Short title in native language	Analisi delle politiche e dei programmi esistenti in materia di educazione e formazione nei settori agroalimentare e forestale
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	In all EU Member States, agricultural education is a national competence and an integral part of general education. Thus, it can be taught as optional courses in some higher education institutions or provided as vocational agricultural education in specific schools. The curriculum content is also widely variable. According to EU published briefings and Eurostat data, only 8.5% of the present generation of European farmers have received full agricultural training, and 70% have only practical experience. In some recent resolutions, the EU parliament stressed the importance of education and training in agriculture, which would enable farmers and agricultural operators to deal with an evolving agricultural sector by learning new skills and diversify their activities. It has been also noted that the centres for education, training and innovation throughout the EU have declined or do not adequately prepare workers to deal with emerging fields and sustainable farming. Also, interaction between research, education and private companies should be enhanced. Even if some measures for agricultural training are available in the common agricultural policy post 2013, a specific policy framework for the strengthening of education in the agrifood and forestry sectors is lacking, with exception of some specific programmes mainly at national and regional level. A better coordination among policy fields and institutions, a major involvement of stakeholders in education, and the use of innovative action-oriented learning methods seems to be the best tools for filling these gaps.
Short summary for practitioners in native language	In tutti gli Stati membri dell'UE, l'educazione agroalimentare è di competenza nazionale e parte integrante dell'istruzione generale. Pertanto, può essere insegnata come corso opzionale in alcuni istituti superiori o fornita come percorso di formazione professionale in scuole specifiche. Anche il contenuto dei curricula è ampiamente variabile. Secondo alcuni documenti pubblicati dall'UE e dati Eurostat, solo l'8,5% dell'attuale generazione di agricoltori europei ha ricevuto una formazione agricola completa e il 70% ha solo esperienza pratica. In alcune recenti risoluzioni, il parlamento europeo ha sottolineato l'importanza dell'istruzione e

	<p>della formazione in agricoltura, che consentirebbe agli agricoltori e agli operatori agricoli di affrontare un settore in evoluzione, apprendendo nuove competenze e diversificando le attività. È stato anche notato che i centri per l'istruzione, la formazione e l'innovazione in tutta l'UE sono diminuiti o non preparano adeguatamente i lavoratori per affrontare le sfide emergenti in un contesto di agricoltura sostenibile. Inoltre, l'interazione tra ricerca, istruzione e aziende private dovrebbe essere migliorata. Nonostante alcune misure per la formazione agroalimentare siano state messe in atto dalla politica agricola comune dopo il 2013, manca un quadro politico specifico per il rafforzamento dell'istruzione nei settori agroalimentare e forestale, ad eccezione di alcuni programmi specifici principalmente a livello nazionale e regionale. Un migliore coordinamento tra politiche e istituzioni, un maggiore coinvolgimento degli stakeholders nell'istruzione e l'uso di metodi di apprendimento innovativi orientati all'azione sembrano essere gli strumenti migliori per colmare queste lacune.</p>
<p>Link</p>	<p>https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-Lc6SsCg4Yp-K86w0ETY</p>

23 PA#23: Results of the survey on “Educational policies on agrifood and forestry systems”

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 23	Partner UNIBO, Italy
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Short title in English	Results of the survey on “Educational policies on agrifood and forestry systems”
Short title in native language	Risultati del sondaggio su "Politiche educative sui sistemi agroalimentari e forestali"
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	<p>The survey was administered to stakeholders, farmers, value chain actors, academic courses coordinators, teachers, researchers, experts, advisors, local and EU authorities and policymakers. The results showed that there is lack or insufficient coordination among the policy fields (pre-university, university, adult learning, and training measures) in the agricultural/food/forestry systems (AFFs), probably due to the rigidity among policy makers and national institutions, the long time necessary for policy changing, and the insufficient coordination among EU, national and regional policies. For all the policy fields, the policies are mostly designed on a country level, followed by regional level. Furthermore, one of the main gaps is that in the different countries the Ministries/Departments in charge for education are separated from those in charge for AFF policy and there is lack of interplay. Other gaps perceived were the lack of networking, efficient sustainability, entrepreneurship and innovative learning methods. The education is also partly separated from the practice and the real needs of producers and AFFs sector, and stakeholders' involvement is still poor. Another gap that emerged was the insufficient amount of financial support provided for the development of educational policy in the AFF sector, especially for adult learning and vocational education.</p> <p>In conclusion, there is a lack of long-term planning in policymaking, lack of budget allocation for this educational sector and of a real policy framework. Thus, policies need to be simplified, to be linked more to practical aspects, and to be revised to suit challenging needs. In this context, recommendations and policy instruments for educational policy framework improving of the AFFs are mandatory.</p>
Short summary for practitioners in native language	<p>Il sondaggio è stato inviato a stakeholders, agricoltori, attori della catena del valore, coordinatori di corsi accademici, insegnanti, ricercatori, esperti, consulenti, autorità locali e UE e responsabili politici. I risultati hanno evidenziato un mancante o insufficiente coordinamento tra le diverse politiche (pre-università, università, apprendimento degli adulti e misure di formazione) inerenti i sistemi agroalimentari e forestali, probabilmente a causa della rigidità tra responsabili politici e istituzioni, il lungo tempo necessario per modificare le politiche e l'insufficiente coordinamento tra politiche dell'UE, nazionali e regionali. Tutte le politiche educazionali sono</p>

	<p>principalmente progettate a livello nazionale o regionale. Inoltre, uno dei principali divari è che nei diversi paesi i Ministeri/Dipartimenti responsabili dell'istruzione sono separati da quelli responsabili per le politiche agroalimentari e forestali e manca un'opportuna interazione. Altre lacune percepite sono la mancanza di network e cooperazione, di un'efficiente sostenibilità, di imprenditorialità e di metodi innovativi di apprendimento. L'istruzione inoltre è parzialmente separata dalla pratica e dalle reali esigenze dei produttori e del settore agroalimentare e forestale, e il coinvolgimento degli stakeholders è ancora scarso. Un altro divario che è emerso è stata la quantità insufficiente di sostegno finanziario fornito per lo sviluppo della politica educativa nel settore agroalimentare e forestale, in particolare per l'apprendimento degli adulti e l'istruzione professionale. In conclusione, vi è una mancanza di pianificazione a lungo termine nel processo decisionale, mancanza di allocazione del budget per questo settore educativo e di un vero quadro politico. Pertanto, le politiche devono essere semplificate, essere più legate ad aspetti pratici e devono meglio soddisfare le esigenze attuali del settore. In questo contesto, sono necessarie raccomandazioni e strumenti politici per migliorare il quadro delle politiche educative in questo settore.</p>
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-Lc6SsCg4Yp-K86w0ETY

24 PA#24: NextFood Sustainability Impact Framework

Nextfood Practice Abstract no: 24	Partner	LU, Sweden
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Short title in English	NextFood Sustainability Impact Framework.
Short title in native language	NextFood Sustainability Impact Framework.
Short summary for practitioners (English) on the final or expected outcomes	Existing frameworks for evaluating impact resulting from agri-food and forestry research provide little incentive for interactive innovation. So there is a need for devising alternative ways of reviewing and measuring performance in this context. In response to this need, the NextFood Project has developed the <i>NextFood Sustainability Impact Framework</i> . The framework is designed to assess: 1) the various effects of practice-oriented research in the agri-food and forestry sectors; 2) the processes of interactive innovation in this context; and 3) their positioning in relation to use and impact. The NextFood Framework renders evaluation as a dynamic (and continuous or periodical) exercise, where stakeholders themselves and jointly specify the impact aspects relevant to their particular contexts. The temporal features of the framework enable a cumulative articulation of impacts in the course of the research work. This provides for learning, as well as for using indicators that correlate with the timing of the work. Using the framework results in an impact index, including a quantitative and qualitative components. While the framework is primarily oriented to evaluating impacts of applied research, the integrated approach of the NextFood project also encourages the making and strengthening of links between research and education. A potential way of using the framework is as a tool for evaluating impact of education programs in the agri-food sector
Short summary for practitioners in native language	
Link	https://platform.nextfood-project.eu/#/case_studies/-Lq2OQ014z9qLC1XP-2-